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Abstract

In an address to the women judges and advocates of the Supreme Court of India, the Chief Justice, NV Ramana, emphasised the need to increase the representation of women in the judiciary. This raises questions regarding representation within the judiciary, and what impact a potential increase in representation would have on the quality of justice and benefits for minority groups. This paper analyses this discussion in the context of Muslims in India. India follows the principle of positive secularism, distinct from the French model of the separation of Church and State, allowing for greater politicisation of religion. With reference to the Hijab ban in Karnataka, the paper shows that the political rhetoric of “saving” Muslim women rarely benefits them, and caricatures them instead to uphold the image of a regressive, barbaric, Muslim community. The disproportionate representation of the patriarchy within Islam is often used to justify violence by Hindutva groups. Further, the paper utilises the Indian Judiciary Dataset by the Trivedi Centre for Political Data to analyse Muslim representation in the Judiciary. Only 15 Muslims have ever held a Judge position in the Supreme Court, of which only 1 is a woman. Similar statistics are seen in High Courts across the country. The paper concludes that it is the State's responsibility to provide an equitable justice system through a diverse judiciary, such as through policy measures to increase representation.

Keywords: Judiciary; Muslim Representation; Secularism; Minority; Women

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Significance of Representation

In the month of September 2021, in an event hosted to felicitate him and nine other newly appointed apex judges of the Supreme Court, the present Chief Justice of India N. V. Ramana addressed the women judges and advocates of the Supreme Court to State his support for increasing the representation of women in the Indian Judiciary. He said “In High Courts, women judges constitute 11.5%. Here in the Supreme Court, we currently have four women Justices out of the sitting 33. That makes it just 12%. Of the 1.7 million advocates, only 15% are women. Only 2% of the elected representatives in the State Bar Councils are women [...] There is no woman member in the Bar Council of India. This needs urgent correction.” (“CJI voices support”, 2021) He said the representation of women in the Judiciary is their right and increasing it would be a step towards undoing the centuries of marginalisation that women have faced.

What is interesting to note about his address is that there was not enough explicit description of why or how increasing women’s representation would benefit the Judiciary. There was a consistent overlying assumption that it is a necessary step towards improving the Justice system. The major direct reason provided in the address was that occupying 50% of the Judiciary was the right of women and this increase should be implemented because women would benefit from the assumption of this right. He said “My sisters (women Supreme Court judges) here have carved out a name for themselves already. My dear sisters, your actions in upholding the Constitution will inspire women, not only in this profession but in all walks of life”. (“CJI voices support”, 2021) Regarding the benefits for the Judiciary itself, he only briefly added that “Ultimately, inclusion of women judges and lawyers will substantially improve the quality of Justice delivery.” (“CJI voices support”, 2021)

The aforementioned statements suggest that increasing representation of women in the Judiciary is deemed to be important primarily because it will encourage women to pursue legal professions and through that, in general, will inspire them to pursue and achieve their professional goals. Such an implication begs the following questions—by encouraging more women to practise law, is increasing the representation of women simply a way to help women achieve their professional aspirations? How would increasing their representation specifically in the Judiciary also have an impact on the quality of Justice meted out by the courts? Would such an increase impact only female beneficiaries of the courts, or improve the Justice system at large? Finally, it inspires the questions that this chapter is concerned with—in a nation-State with an exceptionally plural social landscape, can an increase in women’s representation alone ensure diversity in the Judiciary? Further, does diversity

translate directly into representation? Do women in general represent the interests of women from marginalised communities, such as Muslim women? Finally, does representation necessarily improve the quality of Justice served?

Muslim Women in India - Do they Need Saving?

Very recently, in the month of February 2022, Government Colleges in the State of Karnataka arbitrarily passed a rule to ban the wearing of Hijab by Muslim women on the campus premises. (Sharma, 2022) The reason they provided for this ban was that educational spaces are supposed to be secular in nature and therefore, a neutral uniform devoid of any religious or ideological symbols should be worn by students. It was further added that students who sport religious symbols can cause unnecessary distraction for other students, without clarifying what this distraction entails. This rule was not extended to any non-Muslim religious attires/accessories—such as mangalsutras, sindhoor, bindis, or Sikh turbans—proving that banning the Hijab was an act meant to specifically target Muslim women, a case of what many refer to as “Gendered Islamophobia”. Gendered Islamophobia is a phenomenon where Muslim women in a society are discriminated against and this discrimination finds its roots in historically contextualised orientalist stereotypes about Muslim women—that they are oppressed, and that Islam is an inherently patriarchal religion within which gender equality is impossible to achieve.

In her book entitled *Do Muslim Women Need Saving?*, Lila Abu-Lughod points out that the issue of “Muslim women’s rights” is not an issue that concerns only Muslims and it is important to question who is making use of this issue. (Abu-Lughod 221) The concept of “liberation” of Muslim women is scarcely concerned with actually benefiting them. Rather, it reduces their struggles and instead of understanding the complexity of their problems in modern, post-modern and post-colonial societies, caricatures them. (Abu-Lughod 223) Often, it simply attributes the struggles to Islam and absolves the role of factors external to both, the religious community as well as the socio-political boundaries of Muslim nations. It absolves the role of colonialism keeping alive the narrative of “saving” Muslim women politically benefits different international actors in different ways.

In India, with the sharp rise in Hindutva ideology and right-wing political power in the 21st century, the oppressed Muslim woman narrative is particularly useful in producing an image of a regressive, barbaric and patriarchal Muslim society that needs external State intervention to prevent it from being violent within itself and violent towards others. It is of course true that patriarchy exists in Muslim civilizations and that women and other non-male genders in many Muslim societies across time and space have been oppressed or are continued to be oppressed. It is also true that often, this oppression receives religious sanction and is carried out in the name of Islam.

However, what is important to acknowledge is that rampant patriarchy has been plaguing all societies in the world across time and space and to construct Muslim communities as more intensely patriarchal than other communities is not just a fallacy but a deliberate attempt to construct the religious group as an inherently flawed one. In India, the construction of this image helps the State justify its discriminatory practices against Muslims and it helps justify Hindutva violence against Muslims. Moreover, it helps ordinary citizens believe that the socio-economic marginalisation and ghettoisation of Muslims in India is a consequence of the community's inherent drawbacks and regressive nature, and that State designed policies have no contribution towards the same.

There is nothing unique about the sanction against the Hijab in India, because the infringement on the democratic rights of Muslims is something the country has been witnessing for a long time now. India does not follow the French system of secularism within which there exists a separation of the State and the Church (or Religious Institutions). The nation follows something termed as "positive secularism", a form of secularism where the State protects the plurality of religious beliefs and allows peaceful observation of various religious rituals, beliefs and practices within it. Yet, the claim from enforcers and supporters of the ban is that a religious attire like the Hijab has no place in a secular educational space. What is interesting to note in the case of this recent ban is that when Muslim women started asserting their right to wear Hijab, protests against these Muslim students emerged from among Hindu students. These protests started with Hindu women who began wearing saffron shawls and marched in support of the ban. Soon Hindu men joined these protests and in addition to protesting, they harassed the Muslim women who continued to wear the Hijab.

Data

At the Trivedi Centre for Political Data (TCPD), there is an ongoing effort to produce data that can help arrive at the aforementioned unconditional statistics. The forthcoming "Indian Judiciary Dataset" produced by the TCPD comprises data on Judges and Chief Justices from 25 Indian High Courts and The Supreme Court of India. The dataset includes data on current Chief Justices, sitting High Court Judges, former Judges and Chief Justices of High Courts, from the year 1951 onwards. In addition to information capturing their name, service period, appointments, reasons for retirement and the courts they have served in, the dataset also contains biographical notices on judges which contain information on their education backgrounds (legal education and prior education), history of nominations, gender, religion and whether or not they belong to judicial families. Following are some preliminary statistics from the aforementioned dataset of Muslim representation at Judge level since 1951 in the Supreme Court.

Representation at Position - Supreme Court (1950 - 2021)

Source: TCPD - Indian Judiciary

In the Supreme Court, 1951 onwards, there were only 30 Muslim Judge appointments, 12 Chief Justice appointments, six Acting Chief Justice appointments and five Additional Judge appointments. These appointments also include repeat appointments of the same Judge. When one looks at the number of Muslims to ever hold a Judge position in the Supreme Court, the number is only 15. Of this, only one Muslim woman has held the Judge position. Women who have been appointed as Supreme Court judges have had a total of only 27 appointments across Supreme Court and High Courts in all their careers combined. Of this, only three Muslim woman Judge appointments of Justice Fatime Beevi, the only Muslim woman to be a Supreme Court Judge, took place. However, the number of appointments of the Muslim woman judge is the same as the average number of judge appointments a woman judge of the Supreme Court has in her career, which is three.

Similar dismal representation of Muslims, particularly Muslim women can be seen across High Courts. For example, in Allahabad High Court, the largest High Court in India, the representation of Muslim Judges at different positions is as follows:

Representation at Position - Allahabad High Court (upto 2021)

Source: TCPD - Indian Judiciary

Interestingly, there has not been a single Muslim woman lawyer who has been appointed as a Judge in the Allahabad High Court ever since its inception—a court where historic judgements with regards to rights of Muslim women have been passed. In total, 48 Muslims have been appointed as Judges in Allahabad High Court and of this, zero women have been elevated to the same position.

Conclusion

The aforementioned inequitable justice meted out by the Indian judiciary definitely has an impact on the entire populace and on the quality of democracy of the state for sure. However, if the State has oppressed minorities, this impact is likely to be felt most by that group. In case of India, the Muslim minority has been facing discrimination from the State, and therefore, their requirement for an effective and equitable justice system is presently the highest. The Justice system in the nation claims to protect the rights of Muslim women but through that protection, actively constructs a regressive image of Muslims, which enables violence and discrimination against Muslims at both a political and a sociological level. The dismal representation of Muslim women in the legal system, particularly at the position of Judges in the Higher Judiciary, ensures that the judgements to “save Muslim women” have very little representation of Muslim women themselves. The causes of the lack of representation of the judiciary are not well understood and need further analysis. However, even if the causes are mainly internal to the community, it is the responsibility of the State to ensure the upliftment of the marginalised and provide an equitable justice system through a diverse judiciary. Both of these can be carried out through policy measures in increasing representation, but the choice of the state to not analyse that and work towards it speaks a lot about the complicity of the justice system in further marginalising an already oppressed community.

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